

Creative Economy and Sustainable Development in Developing Economies: Comparative Evaluation of China and United Arab Emirates

Rania Alzair, Victoria Khnouf, Raneem Ghazi ALdeki, Imad-Addin Almasri

ABSTRACT

Sustainable development paradigms need to change along with the economy of the world's most industrialized nations. It has broad applicability because it seeks to resolve problems in the economy and environment, as well as between present and future requirements. We focus on the unique needs of developing creative sectors and economies, which present specific challenges for sustainable growth. This study aims to explore the link between nations' attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals and the expansion of their creative economy. It analyzes sustainability and creativity indices using actual data, along with case studies of China and the United Arab Emirates. According to the analysis, China is leading the world in the growth of its creative economy and creativity metrics. The statistics of China and the United Arab Emirates indicate a level of parity between the two nations in terms of sustainability. The results demonstrate that while China is at the forefront of developing a creative economy, both countries achieve similar levels of sustainability through different approaches. These findings have policy implications.

Keywords: Innovative economy, innovative goods, innovative services, sustainable development, sustainability indexes, area development.

ISSN: 2709-9210

DOI: 10.33168/SISD.2024.0101

Rania Alzair

Banking and Insurance Department,
Faculty of Economics, Damascus
University, Damascus, Syria.
(e-mail: rania.zair@gmail.com)

Victoria Khnouf

Management and Marketing Department,
Faculty of Business, Arab International
University, Damascus, Syria.

Raneem Ghazi ALdeki

Banking and Financial Institutions
Department, Faculty of Administrative
Sciences, Al-Sham Private University,
Damascus, Syria.

Imad-Addin Almasri

Department of Applied Statistics, Faculty
of Economics, Damascus University,
Damascus, Syria

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development paradigms need to change along with the economy of the world's most industrialized nations. Though it has undergone significant interpretations, the phrase "sustainable development" dates back to the 1970s (Romer, 1986; Satterthwaite, 2010). Because it seeks to resolve problems in the economy and environment, as well as between present and future requirements, it has broad applicability. The framework of sustainable growth means the junction of the environment, society, and economy, or the balance between development, equity, and the environment. Advocates diverge, though, in focusing on what should be built, what should be sustained, how to connect environment and development, and how long these initiatives should take.

We focus on the unique needs of developing creative sectors and economies, which present specific challenges for sustainable growth. The innovation economy is driven by information and communication technology and relies more on intellectual capital than physical capital. The broad and cost-effective capabilities of digital technology are beneficial to this sector. The innovation economy is marked by an increasing demand for continuous communication between producers and consumers, as well as a dependence on information for content creation. The United Nations established the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Fund to acknowledge the significance of the creative industries in sustainable development.

There have not been many regional studies that explicitly address the sustainable development of creative economies, despite the significance of the creative industries in economic studies and regional development (Iammarino et al., 2017; Daley, 2001). By analyzing the financial advantages of the creative industries in the context of sustainable development, this article seeks to close this disparity. According to Soini and Dessein (2016), the creative industries play a pivotal role in several sustainable development concerns by advancing inclusive social development, motivating personal accountability for advancement, and nurturing innovations crucial for sustainability. Manioudis and Meramveliotakis (2022) also highlight their critical role in expediting sustainable patterns of consumption and production and augmenting regional sustainable development. The innovation economy supports a non-intensive economic model that emphasizes resource management and economic sustainability, making the relationship between it and sustainable development evident.

Understanding the link between sustainable development, creative efforts, and economic activity is essential, even if they may appear counterintuitive and mutually incompatible at times. This complexity is shown by the many strategies and laws that are represented in the sustainability and innovation economy indices. There is a dearth of empirical data, even though many academics agree that creativity fosters inclusive social development and sustainable growth. By providing insights into

the connection between creativity and sustainability and examining the inconsistencies in their evaluations, this essay seeks to close this knowledge gap. We start with an overview of the research, then analyze the essential questions, compare the sustainability and creativity indexes, and then conduct an empirical study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Moh et al. (2024) utilized a literature research method to identify three main strategies for empowering the creative economy: education and training focused on creativity and innovation, infrastructure and ecosystem development to foster synergy among creative economy actors, and leveraging technology and digital platforms to expand market access. These strategies incorporate sustainable development principles to achieve broader societal and environmental benefits. Based on a literature study, Wibowo et al. (2024) identified opportunities and challenges in implementing digital transformation policies, emphasizing the need for adaptation to local conditions and improved technological accessibility and infrastructure. The effects of the innovation economy on sustainable development are covered in several important studies. Galazova (2016) argues that while the market for innovative items frequently benefits larger capital, which can expand production using new technology, small enterprises are the main forces behind creative output. To strengthen creativity's role in sustainable urban and regional development, academics emphasize the significance of local and regional policy. Conversely, locally generated innovative ideas and cultural traits are necessary for sustainable initiatives (Rodrigues & Franco, 2019).

Wu and Lin (2020) examine the essential aspects of fostering culture and CCIs from the perspective of municipal government. Their study integrates gray relational analysis and entropy weight into an evaluation indicator system that accounts for complexity and ambiguity. The findings indicate that, in comparison to cities in the western region, those in the eastern region and offshore islands have effectively utilized investments in cultural resources. Evaluating sustainable development plays a crucial role in the broader initiative to address climate change. Based on statistical data, the creative economy's contribution to the GDP of developed nations is steadily increasing, underscoring the importance of assessing the impact of local governments on the creative economy's sustainability (Fazlagić and Skikiewicz, 2019). Khussainova et al. (2024) confirmed that transforming the information society and developing the creative economy can mitigate social exclusion risks for youth and older people, fostering new opportunities and solidarities for sustainable development. Kichurchak (2023) examined key trends and contributions of the ICS, using economic indicators and regional specialization indices, and presented a model of ICS functioning across Ukrainian regions, showing the sector's resilience and gradual transformation despite wartime challenges. Yan and Liu (2023) developed cultural impact indicators and a governance framework for the creative economy, demonstrating how humanistic approaches enhance cultural policy effectiveness and support sustainable creative industries. Manioudis and Angelakis (2023) explored how the creative economy supports sustainable development and regional growth in Attica through smart specialization, focusing on the entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP). It underscores the importance of structured smart specialization strategies and inclusive innovation ecosystems in fostering effective regional development.

In a case study of the Baltic States, Štreimikienė and Kacerauskas (2020) examined sustainability and creativity indices to explore the connections between the growth of the innovation economy and the realization of sustainable development goals. The purpose of the CCIs is to advance cities globally, attract capital, and enhance the standard of living for the creative class (Bayliss, 2007). These sectors, deeply rooted in the community, can help rural communities become more economically diverse by employing smart and sustainable strategies such as commercializing art, history, and customs (Cooke & Propris, 2011). According to Howkins (2001), innovation promotes sustainable economic development and forms the basis of the creative economy, focusing on novel concepts rather than extracting limited conventional resources. Social sustainability is a component of sustainable development. The creative and cultural sectors are closely linked to economic sustainability, as creativity plays a significant role in urban economic growth. Therefore, policies that promote innovation are crucial for the sustained viability of cities and regions. Factors associated with the expansion of the creative sectors in the EU are identified by the European Creativity Index. Recent attempts to establish creativity indexes, such as the Cultural and Creative Industries Index (CCII) by Kregzdaite et al. (2020), provide key indicators of the CCIs, including the volume of works created and the financial expression of artistic abilities. These indexes evaluate the creative industries by considering various elements, incorporating input and output variables, rather than focusing solely on the activities within the realms of culture and creativity.

In the following section, we will gather empirical data on the primary creativity and sustainability indices for China and the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Additionally, we will rank these two countries based on sustainability indexes.

III. EVALUATING THE CREATIVE ECONOMY

Among the most active industries in the world economy are the creative ones. UNESCO places a strong emphasis on cultural activities, and its 2009 framework for cultural data is the primary source of information used to measure the cultural economy (UNESCO, 2009). There is no method for evaluating an innovative economy, nor is there a model for creative enterprises that is always "right." Since every nation will have different industries, products, and services within the creative sector, each must choose a strategy that best fits its economic environment. It is crucial that nations identify the various creative industries within their economy and then collect, organize, and systematically assess data on these businesses.

Creative goods include arts and crafts, audiovisuals, design, digital media, performing arts, publishing, and visual arts.

Creative services encompass research and development permits and services, software licensing and services, audiovisual licenses and services, information services, promotion, marketing analysis, architectural design, as well as cultural, leisure, and heritage services.

A structure outlining the essential phases of this procedure is depicted in Figure 1. These phases entail establishing goals, involving relevant stakeholders, conceptualizing and defining the scope of the creative industries, identifying measurement parameters (such as GDP contribution, employment in the creative industries, exports of innovative products and services), accessible information sources, data collection, analysis of the quantitative and qualitative information collected, and evaluation of the outcomes.

Fig. 1: Broad Framework for Assessing a Nation's Innovation Economy (Source: UNCTAD)

Fig. 2: GERD relative to GDP (Source: data.uis.unesco.org)

The lack of standard definitions and comparable information makes cross-national comparisons of creative industry data more difficult. Exports of innovative services greatly outweigh exports of creative items, even though the exchange of creative commodities and services brings in a substantial amount of money for countries. International exports of innovation services totaled \$1.1 trillion in 2020, while creative export items amounted to US\$524 million. The global economy greatly benefits from the realms of culture and creativity, which account for 3.1% of GDP worldwide. According to UNCTAD, the proportion of innovative products and services in the overall products and services exports in 2020 was 21% and 3%, respectively. Furthermore, these businesses account for 6.2% of total employment globally, creating nearly 50 million positions worldwide and hiring a larger demographic of individuals aged 15 to 29 years old than any other industry. The innovation economy fosters the promotion of societal integration, cultural pluralism, and advancement of human capabilities, positioning creative industries as essential to fulfill the objectives outlined in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

GERD, relative to GDP, represents the total funds allocated to research and development activities conducted internally within an organization or country during a specific time frame, expressed as a percentage of GDP. Between 2016 and 2021, China and the UAE demonstrated an increasing trend in GERD, with China exhibiting a notably higher multiplier effect than the UAE. During this period, China's GERD reached 2.4326% of GDP, while the UAE's GERD was 1.49525%, as depicted in Figure 2.

IV. SUSTAINABILITY INDEXES

Assessing sustainability becomes an increasingly complex task as it must encompass three interconnected dimensions: economic, social, and environmental. A key focus of the research was to develop an aggregated sustainability assessment indicator that could capture the most crucial aspects of sustainable development (SD). The main integrated indicators of SD

include the Environmental Sustainability Index (ESI), Environmental Performance Index (EPI), Ecological Footprint, Happy Planet Index (HPI), Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index (GSCI), Sustainable Society Index (SSI), and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) index.

The Ecological Footprint (EF) measures a country's resource consumption and waste generation by assessing the biologically productive land and water required to sustain its population. The Environmental Sustainability Index (ESI) evaluates natural resources, pollution levels, environmental management efforts, and a country's capacity to achieve improved environmental performance, with higher scores indicating better environmental stewardship. The Environmental Performance Index (EPI) focuses on reducing the negative environmental impact on human health, ensuring ecosystem vitality, and proper management of natural resources, with higher scores reflecting better environmental performance.

The Happy Planet Index (HPI), developed by the New Economic Foundation, evaluates the happiness of a country's inhabitants, with higher scores indicating better performance.

The Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index (GSCI) assesses a country's competitiveness through five indices: Resource Management, Ecosystem Resources, Community Resources, Knowledge Assets, and Government Efficiency.

The Sustainable Society Index (SSI) assesses human capabilities, economic welfare, and environmental well-being, aggregating scores into three dimensions: Human, Environmental, and Economic well-being.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Index, developed by the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN), calculates a country's performance by averaging its scores across all SDGs. While the SDG Index is comprehensive and inherently uses weighting factors for each SDG, the number of indicators considered can modify the goals and measures initially defined by the SDGs. Consequently, the evaluation of SDGs may vary significantly based on whether measures are weighted or not.

We analyzed the innovation economy and sustainability measurements. Our comparative evaluation of China and the UAE was based on the ranking of each country according to various sustainability indices. Data on creativity and sustainability indices were gathered and compared for both countries using dashboard reports and other online resources.

V. RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A comparative evaluation of China and the UAE was conducted based on creativity and sustainability indices. Data on both creativity and sustainability metrics were collected and analyzed for these two countries.

Main Exporters. Despite the exceptional circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, there were no significant changes in the list of top ten exporters compared to previous years. China maintained its position as the foremost exporter of creative products, with exports totaling \$169 billion in 2020. Collectively, the top ten exporters accounted for 68.2 percent of global exports in creative products. Interestingly, the UAE dropped out of the top ten list during this period.

Commerce in Innovative Products. Since 2011, emerging economies have consistently surpassed developed economies in the export of creative products. Moreover, a small group of economies collectively contributes to exports of creative products, constituting a majority share of the global total of approximately two-thirds. In 2020, China emerged as the leading exporter of creative products, with exports totaling \$169.309 billion, while the UAE exported \$9.219 billion worth of creative products. China's share of global creative product exports accounted for 32.3%, whereas the UAE contributed 1.8%. Additionally, creative products comprised 6.5% of China's total exports and 2.8% of the United Arab Emirates' total exports.

Trade in Innovative Services. Developed countries have consistently dominated the export of creative services, comprising 82.3 percent of all exports of innovative services in 2020. However, the disparity between developed and developing nations has gradually narrowed in the last ten years. During 2020, the USA emerged as the foremost exporter of innovative services, with exports totaling \$206 billion, while China and the UAE exported \$58.826 billion and \$5.942 billion, respectively. China's share of global innovative services exports stood at 5.5%, while the UAE contributed 0.6%. Furthermore, innovative services accounted for 21.0% of China's total exports and 9.6% of the United Arab Emirates' total exports.

TABLE 1: PRODUCTS AND SERVICES OF CREATIVITY EXPORTERS (2020), (SOURCE: UNCTAD)

Emerging economies	Exports of creative products (\$ million)	Exports of creative services (\$ million)	Proportion of global exports of creative products (Proportion)	Proportion of global innovative services exports (Proportion)	The proportion of creative products in the country's total exports (Proportion)	The proportion of innovative services in the country's total exports (Proportion)
China	169,309	58,826	32.3	5.5	6.5	21.0
UAE	9,219	5,942	1.8	0.6	2.8	9.6

Barriers to Trade in Innovative Services. The absence of essential skills and infrastructure may hinder emerging nations from becoming competitive participants in innovative services. Countries that are leading exporters of innovative services globally, whether industrialized or emerging economies, demonstrate strong performance in indices evaluating workforce

assets, growth, and abilities. Additionally, they possess a robust technological foundation, as highlighted by the UNCTAD (B2C) Electronic-commerce metrics.

Among the top innovative services exporter economies, Ireland stands out with the largest proportion of innovative services contributing to the country's total services exports, accounting for 66.1%. Meanwhile, China and the UAE recorded percentages of 21.0% and 9.6%, respectively.

In studies concerning international trade in services, research has emphasized the beneficial effects of reduced challenges in accessing services on the overall efficiency and effectiveness of service segments within the economy. Segments in services with decreased trading expenses typically exhibit higher productivity and experience greater productivity growth compared to those facing increased trading expenses (Miroudot et al., 2013). Restrictions on services trade have been found to have adverse effects on performance across various significant service segments, as indicated by equivalent metrics throughout a diverse set of nations (WTO, 2020b).

TABLE 2: HUMAN ABILITIES AND ELECTRONIC COMMERCE METRICS IN ECONOMIES EXPORTING SERVICES OF CREATIVITY (SOURCE: UNCTAD)

Emerging economies	Proportion of innovative services in the total services exports of the nation (Proportion)	Skills		Infrastructure			
		Human Capital Index of the World Bank (value, 2020)	Average years of education (2019)	The proportion of individuals who use the Internet (Proportion, 2019 or latest)	The proportion of individuals with an account (Proportion, 2017)	UNCTAD Index for B2C E-commerce (Ranking, 2020)	UNCTAD Index for B2C E-commerce (value, 2020)
China	21.0	0.7	8.1	61	80	55	70.1
UAE	9.6	0.7	12.1	99	88	37	78.2

Main Importers. The world's leading nations importing products of creativity represent nearly two-thirds (63 percent) of global imports in this category. Among the top ten nations importing products of creativity in developing economies for the year 2020, Hong Kong SAR emerged as the largest importer by a significant margin, with imports totaling \$30.493 billion, followed by China and the UAE with imports of \$19.937 billion and \$10.481 billion, respectively. China accounted for 4.3% of global imports of creative products, while the UAE contributed 2.2%. Additionally, innovative services comprised 1.0% of China's total imports and 4.2% of the United Arab Emirates' total imports.

TABLE 3: PRODUCTS OF CREATIVITY IMPORTERS (2020), (SOURCE: UNCTAD)

Emerging economies	Nations importing creative products (\$ million)	Global Contributions: Nations importing creative products (Proportion)	Quota products of creativity from the nation's total importers (Proportion)
China	19,937	4.3	1.0
UAE	10,481	2.2	4.2

The Ranking of China and the UAE Based on Sustainability Indexes. In Tables 4, 5, and 6, the rankings of China and the UAE across different sustainability indices present conflicting findings. This discrepancy is partly attributed to the omission of key indicators representing all pillars of sustainability in existing global aggregate indices, leading to a bias towards certain dimensions.

TABLE 4: RANKING-BASED SUSTAINABILITY INDICES - INTERNATIONAL SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS INDEX (SOURCE: SOLABILITY SUSTAINABLE INTELLIGENCE)

Country	EPI (2022)		Environmental Health		Ecosystem Vitality		Climate Change	
	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank
China	28.4	160	32.8	107	24.5	169	30.4	128
UAE	52.4	39	49.4	55	70.4	3	34	117

Consequently, the undervaluation of specific sustainability dimensions-whether economic, social, or environmental-hampers a comprehensive understanding of sustainability assessments. Moreover, the strong correlation between the main sustainability assessment indices and a country's level of development further complicates the interpretation of results.

TABLE 5: RANKING-BASED SUSTAINABILITY INDICES - ECOLOGICAL FOOTPRINT (GHA) IN 2019 AND HPI IN 2019 (SOURCE: GLOBAL FOOTPRINT NETWORK NATIONAL ACCOUNTS 2020 - A GLOBAL INDEX OF SUSTAINABLE WELL-BEING)

Country	Ecological Footprint (gha) 2019	HPI (2019)	
		Score	Rank
China	3.74	41.9	94
UAE	8.94	34.3	135

TABLE 6: RANKING-BASED SUSTAINABILITY INDICES - ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE INDEX (2022), (SOURCE: ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE INDEX 2022)

Country	Sustainable Competitiveness		Natural capital		Resource Intensity	
	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score
China	30	51.0	116	40.6	141	34.8
UAE	84	43.2	161	34.3	176	26.1

TABLE 7: RANKING-BASED SUSTAINABILITY INDICES - ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE INDEX (2022), (SOURCE: ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE INDEX 2022)

Country	Social capital		Intellectual capital		Economic Sustainability		Governance	
	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score
China	47	51.4	3	68.8	11	52.0	51	58.5
UAE	24	57.0	60	43.1	110	39.7	44	59.3

Table 8 presents a summary of the rankings of China and the UAE in various sustainability indices. Both countries hold comparable positions in their sustainability evaluations based on these indices. When looking at the total number of ranks, it is difficult to ascertain which country has a higher standing.

TABLE 8: FINAL RANKING BASED ON SUSTAINABILITY INDICES (SOURCE: CREATED BY AUTHORS)

Indicators Ranking Sustainability Indices	China	UAE
Sustainable Competitiveness	1	2
Natural capital	1	2
Resource Intensity	1	2
Social capital	2	1
Intellectual capital	1	2
Economic Sustainability	1	2
Governance	2	1
Ecological Footprint (gha)	1	2
HPI	1	2
EPI	2	1
Environmental Health	2	1
Ecosystem Vitality	2	1
Climate Change	2	1
Sum of ranks	19	20
Final rank	1	2

The comparative evaluation of these nations using creativity and sustainability indices unequivocally indicates that China stands out as the top-performing country in terms of creativity and the creative economy. Additionally, China emerges as the best-performing nation across nearly a dozen assessments of diverse sustainability indices.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The arts and cultural sectors are vital for supporting economic sustainability and promoting urban economic development. The goals of our metropolitan areas and regions for sustainable development (SD) must be in line with government policies about innovation. Concepts such as the 'creative turn' and the 'green turn' indicate a movement in public opinion, which is reflected in the growing demand for more sustainable goods and services. Nonetheless, our research indicates that creativity, economic activity, and sustainability do not always align; rather, these aspects of human intention sometimes seem incompatible. Important sustainability indicators like the ESI, EPI, GSCI, and SSCI have a strong correlation with the degree of economic development of the nations they evaluate. Higher-income levels are often associated with superior evaluations according to these indices. Interestingly, there is a correlation between the EFP and HPI indices and income; that is, although there are exceptions, countries with lower incomes typically outperform those with greater incomes.

China is the best-performing nation in terms of innovation and its creative economy, according to comparative studies between it and the United Arab Emirates, based on a variety of creativity and sustainability indexes. Conversely, both nations seem to be in comparable sustainability situations, making it difficult to identify dominance solely based on overall rank amounts.

Among creative hubs, urban areas, and regions, fostering civil society discussions and other peer learning activities can be beneficial. Moreover, enhancing the legal framework for the innovation economy and promoting awareness of the cultural economy is crucial. One approach to achieve this is by revising the provisions for intellectual property rights in the Digital Single Market Strategy.

The examination and comparison of sustainability and creativity indices for a subset of nations over a brief period represent the limitations of this article. Future research efforts could employ advanced techniques like multiple regression and panel data analysis to gain a comprehensive understanding of how the innovation economy impacts the sustainable development of nations.

REFERENCES

- Bayliss, D. (2007). The rise of the creative city: Culture and creativity in Copenhagen. *European Planning Studies*, 15(7), 889-903. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654310701356183>
- Cooke, P., & Propris, L. d. (2011). A policy agenda for EU smart growth: The role of creative and cultural industries. *Policy Studies*, 32(4), 365-375. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2011.571852>
- Correia, C. M. (2014). Measuring creativity in the EU member states. *Investigaciones Regionales= Journal of Regional Research*, (30), 7-26.
- Dabic, M., Potocan, V., & Nedelko, Z. (2017). Personal values supporting enterprises' innovations in the creative economy. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 8, 1241-1261.
- Daley, J. (2001). The intangible economy and Australia. *Australian Journal of Management*, 26 (1_suppl), 3-19.
- Dennis, M., & James, P. (2018). Urban social-ecological innovation: implications for adaptive natural resource management. *Ecological Economics*, 150, 153-164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.04.005>
- Fazlagić, J., & Skikiewicz, R. (2019). Measuring sustainable development-the creative economy perspective. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 26 (7), 635-645. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2019.1651418>
- Galazova, S. S. (2016). Creative industries: Problems of market transformation. *Terra Economicus*, 14(4), 31-41. <https://doi.org/10.18522/2073-6606-2016-14-4-31-41>
- Howkins, J. (2002). *The Creative Economy: How People Make Money from Ideas*. Penguin UK.
- Iammarino, S., Rodríguez-Pose, A., & Storper, M. (2017). Why regional development matters for Europe's economic future. European Commission Directorate General for Regional and Urban Policy Working Paper, 7.
- Khussainova, Z., Kankulov, M., Petrova, M., Assanova, M., Zhartay, Z., Atabayeva, A., & Bektleyeva, D. (2024). The potential of youth and older people's inclusion in the sustainable development of the creative economy. *Sustainability*, 16(10), 4095.
- Kichurchak, M. (2023). Information and communication sector at the core of Ukraine's creative economy: assessing the structure of intercorrelations for sustainable development and postwar recovery. *Формування ринкової економіки в Україні*, 3-18.
- Kozina, J., & Bole, D. (2017). Creativity at the European periphery: Spatial distribution and developmental implications in the Ljubljana region. *Creative Industries in Europe: Drivers of New Sectoral and Spatial Dynamics*, 227-254. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56497-5_11
- Kregzdaite, R., Cernevičiute, J., & Strazdas, R. (2020). Evaluation of creative sectors in EU countries. *Transformations in Business and Economics*, 19, 2A(49A), 21-43. <https://doi.org/10.2861/454308>
- Manioudis, M., & Angelakis, A. (2023). Creative economy and sustainable regional growth: Lessons from the implementation of entrepreneurial discovery process at the regional level. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7681.
- Manioudis, M., & Meramveliotakis, G. (2022). Broad strokes towards a grand theory in the analysis of sustainable development: A return to the classical political economy. *New Political Economy*, 27(5), 866-878.
- Miroudot, S., Sauvage, J., & Shepherd, B. (2013). Measuring the cost of international trade in services. *World Trade Review*, 12(4), 719-735.
- Moh. Yamin Darsyah, Sidderatul Akbar, Widjanarko, & Al-Amin. (2024). Optimizing the role of creative economy in society through literature review: Empowerment strategies and sustainable development models. *Journal of Community Dedication*, 4(3), 529-544.
- Rodrigues, M., & Franco, M. (2019). Measuring the urban sustainable development in cities through a composite index: The case of Portugal. *Sustainable Development*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2005>
- Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002-1037.
- Satterthwaite, D. (2010). The role of cities in sustainable development. *Sustainable Development Insights*, 4, 1-8.
- Soini, K., & Dessein, J. (2016). Culture-sustainability relation: Towards a conceptual framework. *Sustainability*, 8(2), 167.

- Štreimikienė, D., & Kačerauskas, T. (2020). The creative economy and sustainable development: The Baltic States. *Sustainable Development*, 28(6), 1632-1641.
- Wackernagel, M., & Rees, W. (1998). *Our ecological footprint: reducing human impact on the earth* (Vol. 9). New society publishers.
- Wibowo, N. A., Wahyudi, E. J., Ismawati, L., Hermawan, A., & Wardana, L. W. (2024). Opportunities and challenges of digital transformation for creative economy development: Study literature review. *International Journal of Business, Law, and Education*, 5(1), 1369-1380. <https://doi.org/10.56442/ijble.v5i1.569>
- Wu, Y. C., & Lin, S. W. (2021). Integrated approach for exploring critical elements that affect the sustainable development of cultural and creative industries. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 22(3), 596-615.
- Yan, W. J., & Liu, S. T. (2023). Creative economy and sustainable development: shaping flexible cultural governance model for creativity. *Sustainability*, 15(5), 4353.